

DEGRADATION, STIFFNESS REDUCTION AND IRREVERSIBLE STRAINS IN FIBER COMPOSITES SUBJECTED TO REPEATED INTERLAMINAR SHEAR

Kaj B. Pettersson, Jonas M. Neumeister and E. Kristofer Gamstedt

*KTH Solid Mechanics, Royal Institute of Technology,
SE – 100 44 Stockholm, Sweden*

ABSTRACT: Interlaminar shear of a unidirectional carbon fiber/epoxy composite was studied experimentally by use of the tensile IDNS-test setup. The non-linear constitutive behaviour, the degradation and stiffness reduction, under monotonic and repeated loading with successively increasing peak strains was investigated. Shear strains (average values) up to 7-8% prior to failure were observed in the test region together with irreversible strains approaching 3% upon unloading. Hysteresis loops of notable width, increasing with higher peak strains, were obtained. An observable decay in unloading secant moduli (~ 25%) was present whereas such trends could not be discerned in tangent moduli upon unloading from peak loads. To the knowledge of the authors, no previous experiments have achieved global interlaminar shear strain levels of such magnitudes, and also stress levels were higher than obtained with more established methods. Several mechanisms were deemed to contribute to the overall strains; such were higher elastic but also higher irreversible shear strains in the epoxy matrix and the fibers; damage within the epoxy; possibly also in the fibers; appearance of microcracks in epoxy-rich regions; and possibly also separation of the interface. None of these phenomena could alone account for a majority of the obtained strains. Matrix cracks (shear hackles) were found post mortem, but could not be confirmed during the test. Friction-like processes (sliding, viscosity) must have contributed substantially.

KEYWORDS: Interlaminar shear, constitutive behaviour, loading-unloading, carbon fiber-epoxy, optical whole field strain monitoring, stiffness reduction, degradation

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber/epoxy composites and laminates are strong and stiff along the nominal directions, while they are substantially weaker and more compliant in other directions[1-3]. In many practical situations, from a design point-of-view, the relevant loading is shear (interlaminar and in-plane) in addition to tension transverse to the fibers. In many practical applications, shear loading and deformation is deemed to be the most important and critical. Shear properties, particularly interlaminar properties, are comparably less investigated than tensile properties (e.g. shear moduli are estimated/calculated rather than correctly measured[1]).

Generally, it is believed that fibers behave elastically and that densely cross-linked bulk epoxy does likewise. However as an aggregate, notable nonlinear behavior, stiffness reduction (upon unloading) and apparent ductile behavior when loaded to failure are observed in pure shear loading[2]. The purpose here was to study non-linear and degradation behavior in interlaminar shear and to identify and quantify possible mechanisms contributing to the

irreversible strains. The Inclined Double Notch Shear (IDNS-) test[4-6], which is a novel test method to study true interlaminar shear behavior in thin laminates, was used for this purpose.

Failure surfaces fractured of carbon fiber/epoxy composites exhibit shear hackles (or cusps) indicating that mode of separation is indeed shear[2]. In Fig. 1, this mechanism is illustrated schematically and a micrograph of the resulting shear hackles can be seen. This appearance also indicates both a potential weakening mechanism, and that there are substantial ‘plastic’ strains in the fractured epoxy. Precursors to such hackles are oblique matrix cracks in resin-rich regions initiating and propagating perpendicular to the maximum principal stress.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic of how shear hackles arise in resin-rich regions between stiff fibers, and (b) micrograph of shear hackles in a fractured specimen.

Studying tensile stiffness reduction of laminates, elastic behavior is generally assumed up until the point where weaker plies develop matrix cracks and eventually fail. This is especially the case for brittle carbon-fiber/epoxy laminates typically used in aeronautical applications. In most models, only cracking and elastic deformation are taken into consideration. This is a reasonable approximation for typical laminates that contain a substantial amount of 0° and 90° plies. Such laminates typically only see 1-2 % strain before ultimate failure. Prior to failure, the laminate undergoes matrix cracking, where the transverse cracks span the entire thickness of the plies (~ 0.1 mm). The accumulated cracks accurately account for stiffness loss for plies oriented perpendicularly to the load direction. For obliquely oriented plies where shear deformation is notable, this is not the case. Varna et al.[7] observe crack density vs. stiffness loss for $[0/\pm\theta_1/\bar{0}]_S$ laminates. For high values of θ (90° and 70°) the observed crack density correlates well with measured stiffness loss. However, for lower values of θ (55° , 40° and 25°), the damage mechanics model does not give accurate predictions. For $\theta = 40^\circ$ and 25° , no intralaminar cracks are found at any axial tensile load until failure. The elastic properties are, however, found to change with the applied load. This is indicative that a linear elastic description with multiple matrix cracking is inadequate for off-axis plies that are subjected to tensile load combined with significant shear deformations.

Shear deformation at the local fibrous microstructure level need to be considered to understand the mechanisms behind this phenomenon. In axial loading (tensile), carbon fibers are stiffer by two orders of magnitude compared to an epoxy matrix (see Hull & Clyne [3]). However, in shear along the fiber direction, the moduli mismatch between the fiber and matrix is less significant. Since shear testing of individual fibers is not feasible, only indirect measures of the shear modulus of carbon fibers can be obtained. Northolt and Baltussen [8] estimate the shear modulus to be 6-12 GPa for pitch-based carbon fibers, i.e. stiffer, but still in the same order of magnitude as the shear modulus of the epoxy matrix. The high degree of anisotropy of carbon fibers can be understood from the oriented graphitic nanostructure. The wrinkled graphite layers form at turbostratic structure where the layers are primarily oriented along the fiber axis [9]. There are therefore more covalent bonds in the fiber direction. In the radial (transverse) direction, weaker van der Waals bonds between the graphite layers produce a substantially lower stiffness. In a skin-core structured carbon fiber the graphite layers might even slip along each other, resulting in inelastic shear deformation.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The inclined double notch shear (IDNS-) test, was used to load a layered carbon fiber/epoxy composite in interlaminar shear. Test series were conducted as sequences of loading and unloading with progressively increased maximum load to capture changes in the apparent elastic shear modulus \bar{G}_{13} with increased magnitude of shear loading. During the load sequences, surface replicas were taken to monitor the possible evolution of microcracks, fiber breakage, delaminations and other types of occurring damage. In-situ whole field surface strains were measured throughout the entire test sequence by use of an image correlation (DSP-) technique (Aramis of GOM mbH, Germany). Additionally, finite element- (FE-) studies were performed on a cracked epoxy layer. Especially, the change in shear stiffness with an increased crack density was studied.

The IDNS-concept uses the standard double notch compression- (DNC-) specimen (Test Method for In-Plane Shear Strength of Reinforced Plastics, ASTM D 3864). The IDNS test produces very even shear stress and strain fields by minimization of the arising stress concentrations at the notches. This is accomplished by properly combining two load sets (N and M , see Fig. 2) with effects of opposing sign at the notch roots. Details of this concept and the underlying theory, and numerical and experimental verifications can be found in Refs. [1,2,5,6].

The statically determined loading of the IDNS-setup gives stresses which can be determined directly from equilibrium (an absolute requirement for any test method intended for the determination of material constitutive properties). The net interlaminar shear stress in the test region is

$$\bar{\tau}_{13} = N / A, \quad (1)$$

whereas load case M does not contribute to τ . The optimal combination of M and N to produce the most uniform stress fields depends on geometry and boundary conditions. If the notches are modeled as mathematically sharp cracks instead, the entire stress field in the vicinity of the crack tip (notch root) can be characterized by the stress intensity factors K_I and K_{II} . The (symmetrical) mode-I stress intensity is the most important one. Thus, the entire stress field in the crack vicinity can be described by this one parameter (K_I). The correct (proper) proportion among the load-sets is then defined as the one giving:

$$K_I^M + K_I^N = 0, \quad (2)$$

where the superscripts M and N refer to bending and normal loading, respectively.

Proper combination of loads to satisfy Eqn. (2) is a straight forward procedure involving equilibrium, beam theory and linear elastic fracture mechanics. A numerical study of the IDNS-setup and -specimen shows that a careful specimen design, and loading, enables a simultaneous minimization of the mode-I, and minimization of the mode-II singular fields by the use of tilted notches/cracks, with tilt angle γ c.f. Fig. 3 [6].

Figure 2. Principal sketch of an IDNS loading-configuration (a-c), and resulting FE-calculated shear stress profiles for the respective and properly combined load cases (d).

Figure 3. One tilted notch/crack, notch opening $\theta = 0^\circ$, to the specimen centre ($a = b/2$, notch tilt angle γ).

To date, two different experimental setups have been developed for this IDNS-test[1,5,6]. Both setups use specially designed specimen holders to load the specimen at pre-determined positions. The mutual proportion among the tow load sets M and N is in both cases adjusted by inclination of the specimen (with its holders) relative to an external load. Eqn. (2) can then be fulfilled by choosing one single loading parameter: the specimen inclination angle α , see Fig. 4a.

The tensile IDNS setup

The setup used in the present study is shown in Figs 4a-c, see also Ref. [6]. Mutual proportions among the loads are adjusted by inclination of the fixture relative to an external force (F) applied to the fixture by a servo hydraulic testing machine. The specimen is loaded in tension (N) over a grip length $l_g = 30$ mm through knurled surfaces with a rounded edge. The contact pressure is applied by three screws, and a torque of 20 Nm has been experimentally determined as sufficient in order to secure the specimens. Here, no material splitting was observed in the grip regions. The entire assembly of articulated holders and specimen constitutes a detachable unit which facilitates simple and correct positioning of the specimen in the testing device. The forces P are applied with rollers (diameter 7 mm) which rest on recesses, adjustable in the lengthwise direction of the specimen. In order to minimize influence of frictional forces and to preserve nominal loading as the specimen deform throughout a test, the rollers are free to roll along the recesses. External loading is applied to the fixture through two edged tools (edge angle 75°) acting in grooves (opening angle 90°) on the inner perimeter of each fixture half. Thereby, a well defined loading, acting through the specimen center without undesired bending, is secured. Moreover, the setup accommodate for specimen deformation since the fixture halves are allowed to rotate around their respective loading points. For more details on the test setup see [6].

The tests were performed in an MTS servo-hydraulic testing machine equipped with an Instron control system. External load (F) and cross-head displacement were recorded continuously throughout each test by a computer attached to the Instron control unit. Upon loading, the loading rate was 0.002 mm/s, which was deemed sufficiently low to ensure quasistatic loading. In order to capture the shear stiffness reduction with increasing load, unloading sequences were performed to determine the apparent shear modulus \bar{G}_{13} . In order to discern visco-elastic effects, stress relaxation from the sequential maximum load was carried out in some tests. The cross-head movement of the servo-hydraulic testing machine was

paused until the recorded load leveled out. The time duration was up to 20 minutes depending on the load magnitude.

Figure 4a) The tensile IDNS-setup. b) Geometry and loading, c) and d) data overlays with in-situ shear strain fields for two notch distances ($L/b = 1.25$ and 0.8). The rollers used to apply the forces P are also indicated. e) The tensile IDNS test-fixture.

Experimental procedure

Whole field strain measurements were performed with the DSP technique. A high contrast random speckle pattern of carbon powder on a thin layer of white spray paint was applied to the specimen surface. The pattern was imaged before and during deformation by a CCD-camera. The image correlation algorithm compensates for rigid body motions and derives all strain components (ϵ_{11} , ϵ_{33} and ϵ_{13}) in the plane of the sample by differentiation of the displacement field.

The raw strain data may be quite noisy. Therefore, a spatial filter was in some instances used to smooth out noise and strain field artifacts due to surface features etc. Filtering reduces the spatial resolution and fine features and also high gradients in the strain field are then somewhat smoothed out. With the level of filtering used here, strain gradients under the loading points and near the notches were clearly distinguishable. Also, local changes due to uneven contact pressure, surface undulations or material inhomogeneities were in most instances clearly discernible. See Refs. [2,6] for more details on the image correlation technique used here.

Specimens were cut from a pre-existing unidirectional composite panel also used in previous experiments presented in Refs. [4-6]. It consists of 32 layers of Ciba-Geigy HTA/6376C carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy pre-preg. Autoclave curing conditions are 175°C and 600 kPa for 120 minutes. The nominal thickness of the panel is 4.35 mm and the nominal fiber fraction is 65%. Material data for this unidirectional 6367C/HTA-panel is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Orthotropic elastic properties for the uniaxial carbon fiber/epoxy (by supplier)

Young's moduli [GPa]	Shear moduli [GPa]	Poisson's ratios [-]
$E_1 = 140, E_2 = 10$ ($E_3 = 10$)	$G_{12} = 5.2$ ($= G_{13}, G_{23} = 3.8$)	$\nu_{12} = 0.30$ ($= \nu_{13}, \nu_{23} = \nu_{32} = 0.50, \nu_{21} = \nu_{31} = 0.02$)

Specimens with two different notch distances were manufactured: $L = 3.67$ mm and $L = 5.44$ mm ($L/b = 0.84$ and $L/b = 1.25$). Oblique (tilted) notches ($\gamma = 40^{\circ}$) were used in all experiments which was found to give best experimental results[6]. Specimens and notches were cut with a diamond wheel. The specimen end sections and the longitudinal sections were grinded to secure straight and parallel loading.

Net shear stresses $\bar{\tau}_{13}$ (Eqn. 1) were calculated for the actual fracture surface area determined *post mortem* for each specimen separately. Measured notch distance was the distance between the notch roots in the plane of the shear failure. The nominal average shear strain magnitude $\bar{\gamma}_{13}$ was calculated as the mean shear strain over an area stretching between the notch roots and of approximately 0.2 mm in width. Secant shear moduli \bar{G}_{13} were determined according to

$$\bar{G}_{13} = \Delta\bar{\tau}_{13} / \Delta\bar{\gamma}_{13} \quad (3)$$

Continuous loading and unloading curves were obtained by least square fittings of third degree polynomials to the data points from loading and unloading sequences. Similarly, a master envelope for the shear response was generated from data points obtained at the maximum load for every load-unload cycle. Apparent secant moduli were determined for each sequence at unloading. The secant modulus ($\bar{G}_{13,US}$) was taken as the slope of a line stretching to the intersection with the unloading curve at $\bar{\tau}_{13} = 10$ MPa from the intersection of the master envelope and the unloading curve (i.e. specimens were not entirely unloaded, to maintain the correct position of the fixture). Extrapolated curves were used to calculate intersections with the master envelope. Additionally, unloading tangent moduli were derived as the first derivative of the third degree polynomials representing the unloading curves. These were determined at 40 MPa ($\bar{G}_{13,UT40}$) and 90% ($\bar{G}_{13,UT0.9}$) of maximum load. Similarly, loading tangent moduli were determined at a nominal shear stress of 20 MPa and 30 MPa ($\bar{G}_{13,LT20}$ and $\bar{G}_{13,LT30}$, respectively). (Both levels were deemed to be in the elastic regime of the virgin material).

Note that tangent moduli were calculated from fitted curves outside, or near the end, of the experimental data points. Such values must be used with caution, they should (in the absence of further experiments) be taken as indicative at most, c.f. the more erratic shape of $\bar{G}_{13,UT0.9}$ in Fig. 5f. Also the secant moduli were calculated by use of the fitted intersection with the envelope (i.e. also outside the measured range). These moduli, however, are much less sensitive to the choice of fitting parameters.

Surface replicas from polished specimens were taken at different load levels to eventually monitor the evolution of microcracks, fiber breakage, delaminations or other types of occurring damage. The replica system (Repliset by Struers) provides a resolution of details down to 0.1 μm . The replicas were carefully examined both by use of an optical microscope and Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). No trace of evolving damage was detected. However, at this stage it could not be concluded that no such damage evolved.

FE-analysis of crack array stiffness reduction

To estimate the possible shear stiffness reduction due to an array of a periodic array of microcracks a simple plane FE-analysis was conducted. A periodic cell-model representing an array of regularly spaced cracks in a matrix layer of even thickness was used. The cracks were introduced at a 45°-angle between two (infinitely) stiff layers representing the neighbouring stiffer fiber layers with cracks occurring perpendicular to largest principal tensile stress, see also Fig. 1a. Those layers were subjected to a pure shear load and the effective shear modulus for the intermediate matrix layer was determined as a function of the crack density ρ defined as the ratio between layer thickness T and lengthwise crack spacing L , i.e. $\rho = T / L$. The

relative reduction of shear modulus, i.e. $G_{\text{eff,m}}/G_m$, for an isotropic matrix material then depends on only ρ (and is independent of both G_m and T). Neither crack nucleation nor crack growth was considered, merely the existence of such cracks terminating at a rigid adjacent layer. As a rule of thumb based on extensive experimental observations, saturation of crack density is assumed when crack length and crack plane separation are of the same magnitude[3]. In the case of 45° cracks confined in one layer, this corresponds to a value of $\rho = 0.5$, for which $\gamma_m = G_{\text{eff,m}}/G_m = 0.83$ was found, i.e. a reduction of 17%. This configuration severely overestimated the available volume of matrix material available for unloading by such cracks in a realistic three-dimensional fiber-packing of volume fraction $f = 65\%$. Presumably, it also overestimated the highest attainable crack density in such a material regardless of crack nucleation site defects. It thus overestimated the stiffness reduction within the about 35% volume of epoxy matrix. In turn, the layered configuration of proper volume fractions of matrix and fibers constituted a serial one-dimensional stress model, which gave an upper bound to the composite compliance with more complex internal structure. An upper bound to the effective (relative) reduction for the composite shear modulus, γ_{comp} , could then be found as:

$$\gamma_{\text{comp}} = G_{\text{eff,comp}} / G_{\text{comp}} = (1 + c) / (1 + c / \gamma_m), \quad (4)$$

where c is the by volume fraction weighted ratio of matrix and fiber shear compliances:

$$c = (G_f / G_m) (1 - f) / f. \quad (5)$$

Here, the ratio between shear moduli (G_f / G_m) was hard to establish, as transverse properties of the extremely anisotropic carbon fiber at best can be roughly estimated. However, Eqns. (4-5), together with G_f / G_m in the range of 4-10, showed that an estimate on the high side of the composite stiffness reduction was around $\gamma_{\text{comp}} = 0.86$.

RESULTS

Relaxation fracture occurred in some specimens at high loads. Noteworthy is that these occurred at quite different levels of average interlaminar shear strain in the test region. The phenomenon is interesting but was not further investigated here. In Figs.5a-c, a specimen which sustained high magnitudes of shear strain before relaxation fracture occurred can be seen. Figure 5a show the whole field shear strain at 95 MPa and Fig. 5b show the same specimen after relaxation for 23 minutes. During that time the nominal interlaminar shear stress decreased to 91 MPa whereas the average shear strain increased from 4.9% to 6.4%. After unloading to a nominal shear stress of 2.5 MPa, a considerable amount of residual shear strain was obtained (2.5%), c.f. Fig. 5c. After reloading, the specimen fractured in shear after ~ 2 minutes of relaxation to a nominal shear stress of 103 MPa. In Figs. 5a-c, no spatial filtering was used. Notice that the Aramis system gives the shear (angle) in degrees; proper $\bar{\gamma}_{13}$ -values (in radians) are obtained by multiplying values by a factor $\pi/180$.

Nominal (average) strain levels to monitor the constitutive behaviour throughout the entire test were calculated over a narrow region (~ 0.2 mm wide). In Fig 5d, such data from a series of loading and unloading sequences is shown. Final specimen failure occurred at $\bar{\tau}_{13} = 112$ MPa. Each strain data point is not shown individually, instead connecting, straight, lines are plotted. The master envelope, third degree curve fitting, is also indicated. In Fig.5e, the master envelopes for two test series are given (specimens with $L/b = 0.84$ in both). Similar experiments on the same material but for in-plane shear (τ_{12}) can be found in Ref. [10]. The

upper envelope represents a test of monotonically increasing load to final specimen failure at $\bar{\tau}_{13} = 114$ MPa, whereas the lower is the envelope shown in Fig. 5d. Note the similarity in initial slope, final strain and ultimate strength for the two specimens. Additionally, a loading and unloading sequence is shown together with some details for the evaluation of the secant and tangent moduli. In Fig.5f, the different tangent and secant moduli derived from the test series of Fig. 5d are plotted versus the maximum shear strain achieved so far (which is deemed to be the most relevant measure to characterize possible damage). All data are normalized with respect to the initial value for each modulus, respectively. The initial values were obtained at the lowest strain ranges, and those were measured with less accuracy. In Fig. 5f, the discernable trends should be noted rather than the absolute value of the ratio G_i / G_0 . Normalizing values for the moduli were: $G_{0,US} = 3.2$ GPa, $G_{0,UT40} = 3.8$ GPa, $G_{0,UT0.9} = 3.5$ GPa, $G_{0,LT20} = 2.5$ GPa and $G_{0,LT30} = 3.0$ GPa.

Figure 5. Shear strain fields in an IDNS specimen ($L/b=1.25$) at (a) $\tau = 95$ MPa, and (b) at $\tau = 95$ MPa after 30 min, and (c) after unloading to $\tau = 2.5$ MPa (subsequent relaxation failure at $\tau = 103$ MPa). Graphs: (d) Stress strain response for load-unload sequences (with envelope fitted through peaks), (e) fitted envelopes (monotonic and cyclic) with schematic of different (secant and tangent-) moduli for one unload-load cycle, and (f) evolution of modulus measures with maximum attained strain (normalized with first reading).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The tensile IDNS-test enables shear tests in composites along potentially weak planes and thinnest (interlaminar) panel dimensions. In such tests, substantially more non-linear and non brittle behaviour is observed than one would expect from various tensile tests. Here, these aspects were further investigated, in particular for repeated loading and increasing load levels. The amount of non-linearities, the hysteresis-loops, and the irreversible strains, the decay in secant moduli evidenced effects which are not included (nor needed) when modelling and understanding tensile behaviour of such composites. The, with increasing peak strain, increased width of the hysteresis loops indicated friction-like processes within the material. Traditional plasticity does not exist in thermosetting resins, nor is it likely in the carbon fibers. In the transverse direction, however, a carbon fiber exhibits a layered, turbostratic, structure, why internal friction processes are conceivable. Although not identified experimentally on the microscopic level, it is our contention here that both shear strain levels and residual strains to the extents observed in the present material tests must include shear strains accommodated in the fibers, and to a degree substantially higher than assumed possible (or observed) in previous work. Moreover, viscous composite effects, i.e. relaxation, could be seen at load reversal. However, the monotonous stress-strain response did not exhibit any (in principal) different shape than the envelope of the corresponding cycled one (as the highest strains were reached), thus ruling out a purely viscous behaviour. Time-dependent material behavior at sufficiently high stress levels explained why the unloading tangent moduli after reversal from peak load were difficult to extract, and why the reported values, estimated from extrapolated curve fittings to the unloading sequence, exhibited so much scatter/uncertainty that no hard conclusions could be drawn. If measured with better accuracy and confidence, geometrical material changes such as crack-, void-, and/or defect populations and -densities would lower that unloading tangent modulus. However, time-dependent behavior may explain why sparse such geometrical stress concentrators (while not affecting bulk moduli/properties) may locally cause continued damage evolution. This may, in turn, cause individual defects to propagate leading to relaxation failures, as observed for several specimens.

Although matrix micro-cracking (shear hackle-formation) occurs in the final stage (or stages) of a shear test, existence or nucleation and evolution in number of such cracks could not be established from surface replica observations at any load prior to failure. Fracture surfaces of monotonous interlaminar tests on the same material show 70-80% coverage of shear hackles. There, essentially no interface debonding can be seen. Although interface cracks, or -separation, cannot be completely ruled out in a cycled test, it was deemed unlikely that such damage mechanisms explained the decay in secant modulus, or any other stiffness reduction. This conclusion relied on stability considerations; such a mechanism would require stable continuous nucleation and/or growth of interface cracks oriented along straight planes aligned with the test regions over a range of strain levels.

It was concluded that the IDNS test and the presumably unprecedented experimental findings regarding especially the various achieved strain levels revised the general contention about shear deformation mechanisms in carbon fiber/epoxy matrix composites. A number of plausible explanations were presented. However, much further experimental and modelling work is needed to establish governing mechanisms, and their quantitative levels.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors acknowledge financial support from the Swedish Research Council (VR) under contract 621-2001-2764 (KBP and JMN) and 621-2001-2881 (EKG). Material was provided by the Swedish Defence Research Agency (FOI). The Knut and Alice Wallenberg foundation is gratefully acknowledged for financing purchase of the optical DSP-system. Messrs. J. Wikström and B. Dolk (Solid Mechanics, KTH) manufactured the fixture and specimens. SEM microscopy was performed by Messrs. H. Berqvist and P.O. Söderlind (Materials Science, KTH)

REFERENCES

- 1 Pettersson, K.B., Neumeister, J. M., and Johansson, H., “Experimental Determination of Composite interlaminar Shear Properties and Evaluation of the IDNS setup”, *Composites Science and Technology*, In press.
- 2 Melin, L.G., Neumeister, J.M., Pettersson, K.B., Johansson, H. and Asp, L.E., “Evaluation of Four Composite Shear Test Methods by Digital Speckle Strain Mapping and Fractographic Analysis”, *Journal of Composites Technology & Research* **22**, 2000, pp. 161-172.
- 3 D. Hull and T. W. Clyne, *An Introduction to Composite Materials*, 2nd edition, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1996.
- 4 Neumeister, J.M. and Pålsson, A.C., “The Inclined Double Notch Shear Test for Improved Interlaminar Shear Strength Measurements”. *Journal of Composites Technology & Research* **20**, 1998, pp. 100-107.
- 5 Neumeister, J.M. and Pettersson, K.B., “Analysis of the IDNS Test for Composite interlaminar Shear Properties”, *Composites Science and Technology*. In press.
- 6 Pettersson, K.B. and Neumeister, J.M., “A Tensile Setup for the IDNS Composite Shear Test”, *Composites Part A*, In press.
- 7 Varna, J., Joffe, R., Akshantala, N.V., and Talreja, R., “Damage in composite laminates with off-axis plies”, *Composites Science and Technology*, **59**, 14, 1999, pp. 2139-2147.
- 8 Northolt, M. G. and Baltussen, J.J.M., “The tensile and compressive deformation of polymer and carbon fibers”, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **83**, 2002, pp. 508-538.
- 9 Oberlin, A. and Guigon, M., “The structure of carbon fibres”, In *Fibre Reinforcements for Composite Materials*, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1988, pp. 149-210.
- 10 Melin, L.M., and Neumeister J.M., “Measuring Constitutive Shear Behaviour of Orthotropic Composites and Evaluation of the Modified Iosipescu Test”, *Proceedings of Fifteenth International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM-15)*, Durban, South Africa, June 27 – July 1, 2005.